

Granular Capillary Action and Fluidization of Cohesive Powders in a Granular Vibration Pumping System for Handling Lunar Regolith. M. Shahsavari^{1,2}, M. Sperl^{1,2}, K. Shirode³, S. Suzuki³, M. Adachi³,
¹Institute frontier materials on Earth and in Space, German Aerospace Center (DLR), ²Institute of Physics, Universität zu Köln, ³Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University,

Introduction: In space exploration and habitation, In Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) encompasses a range of measures for the collection, transportation, and processing of materials on the surfaces of the Moon and Mars [1]. One of the key challenges in these environments is the handling of very small, abrasive particles called regolith [2]. Conventional methods such as vertical pneumatic conveying, bucket excavation, screw conveyors, electrodynamic traveling waves, and peristaltic mechanisms [3] have been developed for transporting granular materials. However, these techniques encounter numerous challenges when applied to regolith in low-gravity, dusty environments.

Another innovative system for lifting granular materials is the granular vibration pumping system [4], [5]. This system utilizes a granular phenomenon in which particles move upward inside an oscillating pipe, similar to the capillary action of liquids [6], [7]. Additionally, it does not require intermediate media and presents advantages such as improved dust tolerance and reduced maintenance [8]. Further details regarding this method and its underlying mechanism can be found in the studies by [5], [9]. This study aims to experimentally investigate the lifting performance of the system for fine cohesive particles, and for the first time, the climbing dynamics will be discussed in relation to fluidization and decompaction phenomena.

Experimental Setup: The experimental setup of the granular vibration pumping system with two different 2D and 3D sample cells are illustrated in Figure 1. This setup primarily consists of an acrylic pipe, a servo motor, and an eccentric cam mechanism designed to convert the rotational motion of the motor into linear motion, inducing vibrations in the pipe. Additionally, a sample cell was used for holding the granular materials (for detailed specifications, please refer to the literature [10]). In these experiments, the vibration parameters were adjusted to vary amplitude between 3 and 7 mm and frequency within the range of 15–30 Hz. Three different acrylic pipes were employed, each measuring 1 meter in length with a wall thickness of 4 mm, but differing in inner diameters: 8 mm, 16 mm, and 24 mm. The pipes were inserted into the bulk powder to a depth of 75 mm, with the initial height of particles inside the pipe set to 0 mm. The particle diameters ranged between 38–53 μm (D_{50} : $\sim 45 \mu\text{m}$, and the specific density was 2.5 g/cm^3).

Results and Discussion: Figure 2 illustrates the climbing heights of particles sized 38–50 μm , highlighting the effects of the pipe's inner diameter, amplitude, and frequency on the motion of particles. Figure 3 shows the oscillatory behavior of particles within an 8 mm diameter pipe, operating at an amplitude of 3 mm and a frequency of 25 Hz. This is the first observation of cohesive particles climbing in a granular vibration pumping system. Furthermore, the oscillatory motion of particles within the pipe has also been observed for the first time (Figure 2).

Fig. 1. Experimental setup of the granular vibration pumping system with an eccentric cam mechanism (a) [10]. Sample cells with height of $\sim 200 \text{ mm}$: (b) 3D cylindrical type (outer diameter: 200 mm) and (c) quasi-2D type.

Fig. 2 Climbing heights of particles sized 38–50 μm in the pipe with an 8 mm inner diameter, varying amplitudes, and frequencies.

This behavior of particles in the vibrating pipe was probably governed by the principles of consolidation and fluidization in granular materials, as described in [11]. Three distinct phases of powder behavior are observed: consolidation (CS), static fracturing (SF), and dynamic fracturing (DF) as shown in Figure 4. In the CS phase, weak vibrations cause the

powder to form a coherent bulk, where the powder column reaches its most compact and stable state. In this phase, the particles do not climb in vibrating pipe. As the vibration strength increases, the stable voids within the consolidated bulk begin to deform into cracks, signaling the onset of the SF phase.

Fig. 3. The oscillation behavior of particles sized 38-50 μm , in the pipe with an 8 mm diameter (vibration amplitude: 7 mm, frequency: 14, 15, 20 Hz).

In SF phase, particles start to climb within the vibrating pipe. As the vibration strength continues to increase, especially for larger masses, horizontal cracks begin to propagate upward, marking the DF phase. In this phase, the particles stop climbing because they lose their cohesion [12]. The principles of consolidation and fluidization also explains the oscillation of particles within the pipe. As the particles are raised within the pipe and their weight increases, the system transitions from SF to DF region. In the DF region, the particles descend, and as their weight decreases, the system returns to the CF region. This cycle repeats continuously, with distinct differences between the CF regime and the DF regime in the vibrating pipe as highlighted in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Snapshots: climbing of 30-50 μm , within a pipe diameter of 8 mm, with an amplitude of 5 mm and a frequency of 20 Hz, (a) Climbing of particles above the sur-

face of the powder layer – CF regime, (b) CS, SF, DF phases, vs. various powder masses, (c) Stopping the particles' rise at 150-200mm above the surface of the powder layer – DF regime.

Figure 5 illustrates the particle oscillation in a pipe within quasi-2D sample cells. As shown, the particle level on the surface decreases and then increases again.

Fig. 5. The oscillation of glass beads in pipe over time in the quasi-2D sample cell.

Reference:

- [1] K. Sacksteder and G. Sanders, "In-situ resource utilization for lunar and mars exploration," presented at the 45th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit, 2007, p. 345.
- [2] H. Kawamoto, K. Hata, and T. Shibata, "Vertical transport of lunar regolith and ice particles using electrodynamic traveling wave," *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 4, p. 04021042, 2021.
- [3] K. Ashigaki, S. Yoshihama, K. Kato, Y. Yamada, and T. Nakamura, "Research on horizontal, inclined, and vertical conveyance of powder by peristaltic conveyor for developing high-speed printing machine," presented at the 2017 IEEE/SICE International Symposium on System Integration (SII), IEEE, 2017, pp. 781–786.
- [4] H. Kawamoto, K. Kubo, R. Kikumiya, and M. Adachi, "Vertical transportation of lunar regolith and ice particles using vibrating tube," *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 6, p. 04021097, 2021.
- [5] C. Liu, P. Wu, and L. Wang, "Particle climbing along a vibrating tube: A vibrating tube that acts as a pump for lifting granular materials from a silo," *Soft Matter*, vol. 9, no. 19, pp. 4762–4766, 2013.
- [6] T. Akiyama and T. Shimomura, "Investigation of wall shear stress in vibrating particle beds," *Powder technology*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 243–247, 1991.
- [7] T. Akiyama and T. Shimomura, "Measurements of wall shear stress in particle beds when vibrations are imposed vertically along the direction of shear," *Advanced Powder Technology*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 129–142, 1993.
- [8] F. Zhang, L. Wang, C. Liu, and P. Wu, "Climbing motion of grains in vibrating tubes with different geometries," *Advanced Powder Technology*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 356–362, 2017.
- [9] F. Fan, E. J. Parteli, and T. Pöschel, "Origin of granular capillarity revealed by particle-based simulations," *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 118, no. 21, p. 218001, 2017.
- [10] M. Adachi, K. Shirode, N. Hatano, K. Tanaka, and H. Kanamori, "Climbing characteristics of millimeter particles in granular vibration pumping system," *Powder Technology*, vol. 447, p. 120200, 2024.
- [11] P. Sonar and H. Katsuragi, "Decompaction wave propagation in a vibrated fine-powder bed," *Physical Review E*, vol. 106, no. 1, p. 014905, 2022.
- [12] P. Sonar and H. Katsuragi, "Fracturing-induced fluidization of vibrated fine-powder column," *Powder Technology*, vol. 421, p. 118405, 2023.